

Abstracts from the European Academy of Allergy and
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Figure Description: The holotomography images display cells with nanoplastics (NPs) internalized. Images A and C depict maximum intensity projections (MIP) of cells containing NPs, as indicated by white arrows pointing to white dots within the cells: human small airway epithelial cells (SAECs) and human bronchial smooth muscle cells (BSMCs), respectively. Images B and D illustrate the 3D visualization of the same dataset, utilizing pseudo-coloring based on the refractive index (RI) ranges in SAEs and BSMCs, respectively. The objects appearing in red in images B and D, indicating an RI greater than 1.40, correspond to the white objects identified in images A and C.

Conflicts of interest: The authors did not specify any links of interest.

100095 | Binding of food allergens to nanoplastics and their effect on allergic responses

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Background: Micro- and nano-plastic particles (MNPs) are found in water, soil, air, food, and also in humans. There is an urgent need to understand the risks of MNPs in allergic diseases, since they represent a perfect carrier for contaminants and allergens. Here we investigated how different food allergens bind to pristine polyethylene terephthalate nanoplastic particles (nPET), their fate through the first responders, epithelial barrier and antigen-presenting cells, and whether they can augment allergic responses.

Method: Shrimp tropomyosin (TMP), and bovine lactoferrin (LF), unlabeled or with AF647 dye and pristine nPET, produced by precipitation method, were used for the formation of nPET-allergen hard and soft corona. The protein amount bonded to nPET was determined by BCA assay. The effect of nPET on the transport of AF647 TPM and AF647 LF through the epithelial barrier was investigated by Caco-2 monolayer formation in the presence of NPs. The effect on uptake of nPET-allergen corona by monocyte-derived dendritic cells (mDCs) from healthy donors was followed by flow cytometry

and SDS-PAGE. In addition, allergenicity assessment of nPET-hard and soft corona was performed in a basophil activation test (BAT) with three mammalian meat allergic patients and one healthy control.

Results: The amount of allergens that bind to nPET in the hard corona was determined to be 0.08 µg TPM/ µg nPET, and 1 µg LF / µg nPET. Furthermore, the transport of TPM and LF through the Caco monolayer was slightly affected by nPET, where Caco-2 differentiated with nPET transported 1.25 times more TPM and LF than the control Caco-2 cells. In addition, we found that nPET with and without allergen hard corona were taken up by mDCs, and that uptake of allergen in the corona was slightly increased in comparison to allergen only, as determined by fluorescence detection in flow cytometry and SDS-PAGE from lysed cells. Importantly, in BAT nPET showed higher allergenic activity than LF itself in the allergic patients, while no basophil activation was observed with nPET alone or in the healthy control.

Conclusion: Here we show that nPET nanoplastic can bind food allergens and augment the allergic response by affecting the transport of allergen through the epithelial barrier, the uptake and allergen presentation by mDCs, and increasing the allergenic activity of effector cells.

Conflicts of interest: The authors did not specify any links of interest.

100068 | Bovine milk peptide beta-casomorphin-7 alters transcriptomics profiles of gut epithelial cells

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Background: Bovine beta-casein A2 milk is becoming increasingly popular, with both producers and consumers demonstrating a rising inclination towards its production. In the beta-casein locus, alleles A1 and A2 exhibit disparity at amino acid position 67, wherein A1 codes for histidine and A2 codes for proline. The breakdown of A2 beta-casein leads to the generation of beta-casomorphin (BCM)-7 bioactive peptide possessing morphine-like properties. The increasing preference for A2 milk is often attributed to its perceived benefits, particularly its potential to elicit fewer inflammatory responses compared to A1 milk. However, the understanding of this subject remains limited. This study aims to comprehensively examine the effects of BCM-7 and BCM-9, bioactive peptides resulting from the digestion of A1 and A2 milk, respectively, on the integrity of the epithelial barrier.

Method: A microfluidic gut-on-a-chip plate was employed to form a tubular barrier utilizing Caco-2 cells, enabling the assessment of the impacts of BCMs on gut epithelial cells and their barrier

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Binding of food allergens to nanoplastics and their effect on allergic responses

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Background

Micro- and nano-plastic particles (MNPs) are found in water, soil, air, food, and also in humans. There is an urgent need to understand the risks of MNPs in allergic diseases, since they represent a perfect carrier for contaminants and allergens. Here we investigated how different food allergens bind to pristine polyethylene terephthalate nanoplastic particles (nPET), their fate through the first responders, epithelial barrier and antigen-presenting cells, and whether they can augment allergic responses

Method

Shrimp tropomyosin (TMP), and bovine lactoferrin (LF), unlabeled or with AF647 dye and pristine nPET, produced by precipitation method, were used for the formation of nPET-allergen hard and soft corona. The protein amount bonded to nPET was determined by BCA assay. The effect of nPET on the transport of AF647 TPM and AF647 LF through the epithelial barrier was investigated by Caco-2 monolayer formation in the presence of NPs. The effect on uptake of nPET-allergen corona by monocyte-derived dendritic cells (mdDCs) from healthy donors was followed by flow cytometry and SDS-PAGE. In addition, allergenicity assessment of nPET-LF hard and soft corona was performed in a basophil activation test (BAT) with three mammalian meat allergic patients and one healthy control.

Results

The amount of allergens that bind to nPET in the hard corona was determined to be 0.08 µg TPM/ µg nPET, and 1 µg LF /µg nPET. Furthermore, the transport of TPM and LF through the Caco-2 monolayer was slightly affected by nPET, where Caco-2 differentiated with nPET transported 1.25 times more TPM and LF than in the control Caco-2 cells. In addition, we found that nPET with and without allergen hard corona were taken up by mdDCs, and that uptake of allergen in the corona was slightly increased in comparison to allergen only, as determined by fluorescence detection in flow cytometry and SDS-PAGE from lysed cells. Importantly, in BAT nPET-LF showed higher allergenic activity than LF itself in the allergic patients, while no basophil activation was observed with nPET alone or in the healthy control.

Conclusion

Here we show that nPET nanoplastic can bind food allergens and augment the allergic response by affecting the transport of allergen through the epithelial barrier, the uptake and allergen presentation by mdDCs, and increasing the allergenic activity of effector cells.

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